

PSYCHOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT REPORT

Name: A. A
Father's Name: Aftab Ahmad
Date of Birth: 14 September 2004
Assessment Dates: 20,21,22, 24, 25 October 2022
Assessed By: Mahnoor Fatima
Case No: 01

IDENTIFYING INFORMATION

The client was 18-year young female. She is a student of intermediate. She has 3 siblings, she has one sister and two brothers her birth order is 2nd, Her other siblings also students and lived with client. Father of client is a businessman and mother is housewife. Her parents are literate. She lives in individualistic family structure the earning member is father and she belongs to elite class. The relationship with family members is not satisfactory.

REFERRAL SOURCES AND PRESENTING COMPLAINTS

The client is taken from hospital; she is referred by her mother. The client comes to hospital for psychological assessment and treatment. According to client complains reported by her that was suicidal attempts and self-harm, loss of interest, irritability, hopelessness, lack of interest, loss of appetite, insomnia, headache, worthlessness, aggression and sadness, some presenting complaints as reported by her mother are swooning, aggression and self-harm.

INTERVIEW INFORMATION

The client's history of illness is present from last one years. One years ago she was in relation with a male friend. He cheats her, her views about the friends are negative, she is much dependent on friends. Her sister is also involved in immoral activities, she reported that she told to mother about all these immoral activities, restrictions are increased to sister and she becomes enemy, according to her she feels bad always, after some time her mother knows about her relation and yelled at her. Now she was quite depressed, needed some emotional support but her mother criticizes her due to these activities.

According to client's mother apparently her first cry at birth time. Start neck holding at the age of 4 months, sitting at the age of 6 months, crawling at the age of 9 months and walking at the age of 11 months. She achieved her milestone at proper age.

According to client she is 18 years old female. She is a student of intermediate. She has 3 siblings. She has 1 sister and has 2 brothers. Her birth order is 2nd. She belongs to an elite class family and lives in city Sargodha. Parents both are literate and her father is a businessman and mother is a house wife.

According to client the family system of is individualistic. the total family members of client are 6. The earning member of family is father; he is a businessman. Father remarried but after some time divorced, due to this reason she has conflict with her father. She is aggressive and not tolerate. She has conflicts with her sister, she is emotionally attached to family and her sister also has issues with father, she wants to love marriage but father is not willing due to cast issues. Her father is angry with her sister due to her immoral activities.

According to client she started her schooling at the age of 5 years, she is an brilliant student at school she never got position in school. She is matric passed and now is an intermediate student. The client's relationship with her teachers and class fellows was very friendly, according to her the friends were lovely she enjoyed more with them, she was not interested in games during school life. She emotionally attached to friends and don't share them to with anyone other in school.

The client has many friends but has not satisfactory relationship with them. She told me that one years ago she was in relation with a male friend. He cheats her, her views about the friends are negative, she is too much dependent on friends. She becomes emotionally attached to friends and this caused distress, she can't share friends. The client is with histrionic personality disorder and there is no any other medical or psychiatric illness reported in the family.

BEHAVIOR DURING TESTING SESSIONS

The client behavior during the interview was anxious. Her appearance was good, she was wearing clean clothes, and self-care was average. Her way of talking was confident, she was cooperative. She was more talkative but discussed her problem in a normal way. She rarely made

an eye contact. She showed little resistance for testing but the therapist encouraged him and provides importance of testing. She was irritable during the administration of SPM that it's a quite lengthy test but on providing encouragement she does this. On sitting the chair, she was feeling restlessness and could not maintain her attention on the work. Speech was slightly disturbed. Thought was negative. Mood was low and restless. There is no delusion or hallucinations present. She was able to explain that what is the time and place. The subject's short-term memory was good. The subject's attention and concentration was disturbed. She had no insight about her illness.

TEST ADMINISTERED

- Slosson Drawing Coordination Test (SDCT)
- Standard Progressive Matrices (SPM)
- Human Figure Drawing (HFD)
- Depression Anxiety Stress Scale (DASS)
- Rotter's Incomplete Sentence Blank Test (RISB))
- Thematic Apperception Test (TAT)

PSYCHOLOGICAL EVALUATION

Slosson Drawing Coordination Test (SDCT). Test is a neurological screening test and used for to check eye hand coordination the client obtained 100% accuracy scores that indicates the client's eye hand coordination is intact.

Standard Progressive Metrics (SPM). A test for abstract thinking and logical reasoning (it is one aspect of intelligence) the client obtained 50 scores and 75% percentile rank which indicates that client is intellectually above average fall in grade +III.

Human Figure Drawing (HFD). Test is a projective drawing test which indicates that the client has difficulty in reaching out into the world or towards others, aggressiveness, intense inadequacy, very poor self-concept, fearfulness, insecurity, anxiety, stubbornness, emotional immaturity, dependency and depression. instability, impulsivity, poor integration, regression due to emotional disturbance.

DASS is a depression, anxiety and stress scale (DASS). Test which measures these three things the scores in DASS indicated that the client falls in extremely severe category of these three.

Rotter's Incomplete Sentence Blank (RISB). Test is a semi projective test the cutoff scores of this test is 135 and the client obtained scores are 186 which indicated that client is maladjusted with her environment.

Thematic Apperception Test (TAT). TAT is a projective psychological test which indicates that client has the needs of aggression, socurance, achievement, nurturance, affiliation, freedom, and sex. The presses aggression and socurance. The anxieties are disapproval, loneliness, helpless, deprivation and lack of love. The main defenses of TAT that are used are repression, isolation, and projection. The most common sources of conflict for clients are authority figures such as parents. Client accounts reveal a lack of reality contact and a threatening and congenial environment.

TENTATIVE DIAGNOSIS

(F33.0) Major Depressive Disorder, mild with melancholic features

PROGNOSIS

The client's prognosis was poor. Because her motivational level is low and she has no insight of her problem. He has guilt feelings, suicidal ideation, suicidal attempts and wants to overcome it. Family is not supportive.

CONCLUSION

The client is 18 years' young female. She is student, her relationships with her parents and siblings are not good. Her presenting complaints as reported by him loss of interest, suicide attempts, self-harm, irritability, hopelessness, lack of interest, loss of appetite, insomnia, headache, worthlessness, aggression and sadness. Some psychological tests were administrated on the client which indicates she has personality problems, conflicts, depression and some feature of anxiety. She seems to suffered from Major depressive disorder mild with melancholic features according to the DSM-5-TR.

RECOMMENDATION

This client might benefit from cognitive behavior therapy to help him control her behavior and beliefs. It is necessary to teach him how to work with target goals and how to change his abnormal behavior.

- Aggression management techniques were used to deal with his rage.
- Psycho-educate the client about his problem through psychotherapy.
- Psycho-educate the client's family on how to support him in changing her behaviors, or better relationships, family therapy is essential.
- Social skills are essential for engaging in a variety of healthy and positive activities, as well as improving her negative behaviors and maximizing her time.
- Behavioral management techniques, such as how to express her feelings, emotions to others, and how to communicate with others, would be the best for her.

Note: The report is only valid for academic purposes. This report will not be considered for any legal action, legal facilitation, medication, and other external affairs.

Treatment Plan

Case No	01	Client's Name	A.A	Age	18Y	Gender	Female
----------------	----	----------------------	-----	------------	-----	---------------	--------

Symptoms	Self-harm, irritability, hopelessness, lack of interest, loss of appetite, insomnia, headache, worthlessness, aggression and sadness, suicidal ideation
Diagnosis	(F33.0) Major Depressive Disorder, mild with melancholic features
Target Symptoms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-harm • Hopelessness • Lack of interest • Worthlessness • Aggression • Sadness • Suicidal ideation

Treatment approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cognitive behavioral therapy • Client centered therapy • Educative and supportive therapy 		
Frequency of sessions required	1 per week	Proposed number of sessions to achieve goals	25-30
Major Treatment Goals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasingly verbalize hopeful and positive statements regarding future. • Utilize behavioral strategies to overcome depression • Conflict resolution skills to resolve interpersonal problems • Increase assertive communication. • Minimize the self-harm. • Educate about sleep hygiene. • Verbalize the feeling of anger in a controlled, assertive way. 		
Interim Treatment Goals for target Symptoms	Number	Expected Time To achieve	
	1.Establish working relationship with the client.	2	
	2.History taking from client and family	2	
	3.Work on hopelessness and helplessness	1	

	4.Stabilize the suicidal crises and self-harm	2
	5. Psychological testing	5
	6. Identifying the automatic thoughts	2
	7.Replace the negative thoughts and counseling regarding family.	2
	8. Post testing	
Initial Phase	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish working relationship • Long terms goals and work for them • Give unconditional positive regard to the client • Educate about therapy • Provide motivation • Acceptance of client for change and mutual work is very necessary <p>Defining the goals of therapy</p>	
Middle Phase	<p>Exploring the reasons of problem</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To explore the environmental hazards and stressors • Explore the reasons for maladaptive behavior and thinking • What are the negative thinking and what are the reasons for these negative thoughts? • Probing history to access complete understanding of the problem • Factors which are triggering and reinforce his negative behavior <p>Coping Strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve interpersonal relationships • Engage in activities which make him busy 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Communication strategies <p>Task management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• It will improve decision making power of the client how to maintain her time table and preferable activities• Muscle relaxation and assertive training
Termination Phase	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Analyzing the dependency level of client on therapist• How much he became assertive• Goals achieved or not, which goals are achieved and which need to work again• How much became independent and normal• Follow up session